

Type and level of production provided by the requestor

Type of production: Broiler; Other poultry; Laying Hens

Level: Transportation; Killing

Keywords: Handling, killing method, cervical dislocation, unconsciousness

Background context provided by the requestor

During catching prior to transport cervical dislocation of poultry that are not fit for transport is often performed by “swirling” the poultry around. It has come to our attention that this is not necessarily the best way to kill the animals as you risk them not being correctly stunned during the “swirling” procedure and thus, not ensuring an actual disconnection in the neck.

Question raised by the requestor

We would like to know:

1. If there are any studies in relation to the “swirling” method covering, e.g. if there are any risks of it not being an effective method to stun and kill the animal, and/or if there are any general welfare concerns with this method (and if yes; please elaborate). And if relevant, how should it be performed to ensure that the animal is killed properly, i.e. is there anything you should consider if using this specific method.
2. How cervical dislocation (as an alternative to swirling) is performed correctly in poultry. There are different methods and therefore, we would like to know if any of them are better suited than others to ensure the animals welfare, including ensuring that they are killed correctly (based on indicators of death, consciousness and pain).

Preferably, our inquiries should consider both manual and mechanical cervical dislocation for poultry. Moreover, for both of the above inquiries it would be preferred if they considered all weight groups of domestic fowl, however, the heavier groups are the main priority (i.e. broilers (end stage) and/or broiler breeders, laying hens etc.)

Answer

- 1. If there are any studies in relation to the “swirling” method covering, e.g. if there are any risks of it not being an effective method to stun and kill the animal, and/or if there are any general welfare concerns with this method (and if yes; please elaborate). And if relevant, how should it be performed to ensure that the animal is killed properly, i.e. is there anything you should consider if using this specific method.**

“Swirling” is a technique aimed at inducing manual cervical dislocation in poultry by applying mechanical rotational force to cause loss of consciousness, potentially resulting in dislocation of the cervical vertebrae and subsequent spinal cord disruption. The video submitted by the requestor illustrates the procedure, wherein the operator secures the bird by the head and rapidly rotates its body in a circular motion. However, **no scientific studies or detailed descriptions** of this method have been found. Therefore, the authors can only speculate about its outcomes and implications for animal welfare.

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This method potentially causes pain and fear. The primary issue lies in the method requires **lifting the animal by the head** and spinning its body. This action can induce considerable pain and fear, as the bird is raised by the head before cervical dislocation. Heavier birds or those with abnormalities, are at greater risk because the additional weight of their bodies, when lifted by the head, increases the strain on their necks and may lead to a higher likelihood of injury and discomfort.

[EFSA \(2004\)](#) highlighted that cervical dislocation does not consistently induce immediate unconsciousness in all birds, raising significant animal welfare concerns. In such cases, death may occur by asphyxiation rather than through a rapid loss of brain function.

2. How cervical dislocation (as an alternative to swirling) is performed correctly in poultry. There are different methods and therefore, we would like to know if any of them are better suited than others to ensure the animals welfare, including ensuring that they are killed correctly (based on indicators of death, consciousness and pain).

Cervical dislocation is used to kill poultry by stretching and twisting the neck of the animal, causing unconsciousness through concussion and death by cerebral ischemia. According to [Gregory and Wotton \(1990\)](#), for cervical dislocation to be effective, this technique must result in the dislocation of the cervical vertebrae (ideally C0-C1), leading to the separation of the skull from the spine and the rupture of the major blood vessels supplying the brain.

Cervical dislocation may be carried out either manually or using mechanical devices. According to [Council Regulation \(EC\) No 1099/2009](#), within the EU, this method is limited to 70 birds per person per day in order to minimize errors linked to operator fatigue. The regulation also specifies that manual cervical dislocation is permitted only for birds weighing up to 3 kg. For birds between 3 and 5 kg, the method must be applied mechanically. Cervical dislocation is not permitted for birds weighing more than 5 kg.

Even though cervical dislocation is authorized under European legislation as a method for killing poultry, does not always lead to immediate unconsciousness and, in some cases, can cause death by asphyxiation before the bird loses consciousness. Neck crushing does not sever the common carotid arteries and does not reduce its diameter. Therefore, it does not cause cerebral ischaemia and hence loss of consciousness. If the spinal cord is severed without stopping blood supply to the brain, it results in death from asphyxia.

As mentioned earlier, given these concerns, **EFSA does not recommend** the use of cervical dislocation as a standard method for stunning or killing poultry. Instead, alternative techniques such as captive bolt stunning or electrical stunning are preferred, depending on species-specific and operational conditions. These methods are generally considered to provide a more reliable and humane induction of unconsciousness.

Those seeking more detailed guidance on the **correct application** of cervical dislocation may consult the [European Commission's 2018 factsheets on animal welfare at the time of killing](#), as well as the EFSA's [2004 opinion related to welfare aspects of the main systems of stunning and killing the main commercial species of animals](#) and [2019 scientific opinion on the killing of poultry for purposes other than slaughter](#).

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Conclusions

- "Swirling" method is intended to induce manual cervical dislocation by spinning the bird's body while holding it by the head. However, it **lacks scientific validation of the effectiveness in causing immediate unconsciousness followed by dead or standardized descriptions**.
- The method causes **pain and fear** when birds are handled by the head and swung, especially in heavier or physically compromised animals.
- Cervical dislocation does **not induce immediate unconsciousness**. In some cases, birds may die from asphyxiation before losing consciousness.
- The method is **not recommended** due to animal welfare risks. More humane and effective alternatives (such as captive bolt or electrical stunning) are preferred depending on operational conditions.

AI disclaimer

The authors declare having used ChatGPT to check the English grammar of the initial English version.

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